

ABOUT ALISHER NAVOI'S SKILLS IN CREATING THE IMAGE OF FARHOD

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ABSTRACT

Navoi promotes the idea of friendship of peoples through the characters of Farhad, Shirin and Shapur. Farhad's love for the Armenian girl Shirin and his friendship with Shapur from Iran are a vivid example of the idea of friendship between peoples. Narrating the bravery of Navoi Farhad in an artistic way, he combines his services to the prosperity and peace of the country, people's well-being and science in deep verses.

In the epic "Farhod and Shirin", the poet glorifies the ideas of true love and loyalty, friendship and loyalty, work and creativity, patriotism and heroism. The epic is not written for young people and children, but many chapters of the work are dedicated to the life of children and young people and their education. In the epic, the poet described Farhad's love for science and work from his childhood with great skill and deep sincerity. This shows that Navoi paid great attention to the upbringing of the child and his education. Farhad grew up to be a very smart and intelligent boy from a young age. He studies at school with great passion and diligence. He soon learns science, mathematics, and logic. Sensing young Farhad's passion and love for science, his parents consider it appropriate to give him education. Famous scientists of the world give lessons to Farhad in various subjects. As a result, the most complex and secret sciences fully reveal their secrets to him. He studies diligently and patiently and becomes a knowledgeable and intelligent person. By describing his life in such vivid scenes, the poet Farhad calls for special attention to the education of children. Farhad is described as having the ability to immediately understand whatever subject he studies:

If a layer saw a lesson,

There was no need to open the page again.

What can I say, read it and write it down in your heart,

Dema's heart is on the world record.

At that time, children were dry, memorized lessons. Children did not even understand the meaning of what they memorized. At such a time, Navoi encouraged children to be interested in science and to understand the meaning of what they read.

The motto of reading, reading,

In memory of the mold, go to the safhasafha...

It is noted that as a result of Farhad's diligent reading and understanding of its meaning, he acquired a lot of knowledge: There is no knowledge in the world that is not enough, Knowledge that is not enough to acquire knowledge. In this way, Navoi calls children to master knowledge thoroughly and shows the ways of educating and growing them as a great pedagogue and coach. In addition, the saga depicts Farhad as a physically fit young man. He loves to learn the secrets of swimming, horse riding and fencing. Alisher Navoi described Farhad, who was devoted to science from a young age and was physically fit:

The demon is pure of heart and pure of eyes,

His tongue is pure, his words are pure, he is pure, and he gives the image of a mature young man who is perfect in every way, spiritually and physically beautiful. He also praises Navoi Farhad as a young man who has a great passion for work and craft, who has mastered the arts of carpentry, painting, and painting. Possessing knowledge and craft, physically fit, Farhad will grow up to be a caring, honest, brave and noble, brave person. Under the leadership of Farhad and as a result of his direct selfless work, a large canal ("River of Life") and a pond ("Sea of Salvation") are dug. Navoi describes Farhad as a hero who brought water to waterless lands, a young man who performed miracles in the field of work. He believes that science and craft should be served for the benefit of the people.

When Farhad goes to Armenia in search of Shirin, he sees people working hard to dig a canal in the mountains in the Armenian land and says: The master of the craft is the end, the end is the end of the soil. - he uses his knowledge, skill and enthusiasm, relieves the hardships of the canal diggers and gains great fame among the people. The important qualities of this hero are his feelings of heroism, patriotism, patriotism and friendship. Farhad fights for the well-being of the country and bravely defeats the enemies who cause harm to people. In addition, Navoi promotes the idea of friendship between peoples through the characters of Farhad, Shirin and Shapur. Farhad's love for the Armenian girl Shirin and his friendship with Shapur from Iran are a vivid example of the idea of friendship between peoples.

Narrating the bravery of Farhad in an artistic way, Navoi combines his services to the country's prosperity and peace, people's well-being, and science in deeply meaningful verses: "Ki to olam, binisi boldi bunyod, Bu glagig izali izdi, amizod." Alisher Navoi's epic "Farhod and Shirin" advanced human qualities and humanitarian ideas have a deep impact on the spirituality of young readers and serve to make them a necessary person for the people and the country. The great poet expressed his thoughts on the education and upbringing of children in the epic "Layli and Majnun". Navoi, who promoted the idea of building new schools, dreams that girls will study in the schools along with boys. Alisher Navoi, through his Farhad, Qays, Iskandar and other positive characters, emphasizes the great power of education in the development of a child.

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